

Shape Memory Alloy Prestressing of Fiber-Reinforced and Ultra-High-Performance Concrete for Bridge Truss Members

Alexander Chen¹, Bassem Andrawes^{1,*}

¹[University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, Urbana, IL, USA]

*Corresponding Author: Bassem Andrawes, andrawes@illinois.edu

Abstract:

This research focused on addressing cracks in concrete trusses in bridge structures using shape memory alloys (SMAs). Shape memory alloys recover from inelastic deformation when exposed to elevated temperatures. This was studied for utilization in two ways. By embedding SMA bars inside concrete and subsequently heating, the concrete is prestressed, and cracks are delayed. Alternatively, heating the SMA after cracking occurred resulted in crack closure. Thirteen small-scale flexural specimens were fabricated from mortar, fiber-reinforced concrete (FRC), and ultra-high-performance concrete (UHPC) to verify these two concepts. The healing approach reduced crack widths by as much as 80%, 90%, and 84% in the mortar, FRC, and UHPC specimens, respectively. This study then applied the SMAs in a larger test specimen. A main advantage of SMA prestressing over conventional prestressing is the elimination of end anchorage equipment. This allows more freedom in placement and makes it appealing for use in concrete truss systems. A large-scale precast truss was fabricated to demonstrate the concept. Voids were introduced into the web of a precast girder to alter its structural behavior to that of a Howe truss. SMA bars were embedded in a vertical member where large tensile forces are expected during loading. The SMA was activated, and an average compressive strain of $301 \mu\epsilon$ was measured. The load corresponding to cracks in the prestressed member was 600% higher than that of the member with only conventional steel.

1. INTRODUCTION

Concrete is a popular material in transportation infrastructure due to its high compressive strength. However, it is prone to cracking from shrinkage, temperature changes, or extreme loads (ACI, 2007). These cracks expose the internal steel reinforcement to corrosion, which jeopardizes the structures' integrity (Lopez-Calvo et al., 2018; Otieno et al., 2010; Poursaeed & Ross, 2022). Thus, this research aimed to mitigate concrete cracking through the use of shape memory alloys (SMAs). SMAs recover from inelastic deformation when heated past their transformation temperature. This study used this property in two primary ways. The first method was to prestrain an SMA bar and embed it inside concrete during casting. After the concrete was cured, the SMA bar was heated to prestress the concrete. This produced localized prestressing forces that delayed the onset of cracks in concrete. The second method also involved embedding a prestrained SMA bar inside concrete. The SMA bar is heated after cracking has occurred rather than before, to heal the concrete through crack closure. Thirteen small-scale flexural specimens were manufactured and tested to evaluate the use of SMA in mortar, fiber-reinforced concrete (FRC), and ultra-high performance concrete (UHPC). The SMA prestressing method was then applied in a large-scale concrete truss to experimentally validate its use for geometrically optimized concrete structures. SMA bars were embedded in a vertical member of the truss where the greatest tensile forces were expected. The bars were subsequently heated with an induction heater to prestress the concrete member.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Shape Memory Alloys

Shape memory alloys have the ability to reverse inelastic deformation upon heating (Lagoudas, 2008). This property is referred to as the “shape memory effect” and has been used by researchers to prestress concrete. An SMA bar is first prestrained by stretching until it is inelastically deformed. The bar is then embedded in concrete during casting. Once the concrete is cured, the SMA is heated to trigger its shape memory effect. The stress produced as the SMA attempted to recover its original length transforms into prestressing inside the concrete (Maji & Negret, 1998; Pérez-Claros & Andrawes, 2025; Sung & Andrawes, 2021). This method allows a greater degree of flexibility in placement when compared to conventional steel prestressing because large anchorage equipment is not needed. A similar approach can be used to heal the concrete instead of prestressing it. When embedded SMA is heated after cracking occurs, it pulls the crack closed (Sun et al., 2013). This differs from other approaches to concrete healing, which fill the crack. For example, researchers incorporated microcapsules with a healing agent into the concrete. When the concrete cracks, it ruptures the capsules and the healing agent solidifies in the cracks (Wang et al., 2025). This study used SMAs to avoid the issue of maintaining residual deformations in the structure.

2.2 Heating Methods

SMAs require an increase in temperature to activate their shape memory effect. Two heating methods were used in this study. The first method involved running a current through the SMA. A portable power supply was connected to the exposed ends of the SMA bar with metal clamps (**Figure 1a**). A current was then passed through the SMA, heating it through electrical resistivity. The second method relied on electromagnetic induction. A copper coil was attached to the work head of an induction heater (**Figure 1b**). A current was passed through the coil, which generated magnetic fields around the coil. These magnetic fields produced eddy currents in the SMA bar and heated it without direct contact. The advantages and disadvantages of each method for activation in the different mix designs were investigated.

Figure 1. Heating of specimens using (a) electrical resistivity and (b) electromagnetic induction.

3. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 SMA Prestressing and Healing in FRC and UHPC Specimens

Thirteen small-scale flexural specimens were fabricated for this study. The dimensions of the specimens were 1.25" x 2" x 10" as seen in **Figure 2**. A 0.25"-diameter SMA bar was used as the flexural reinforcement. Six copper crimps were added along the length of each bar to improve its bonding behavior with the concrete. A notch was added to the bottom center of the specimen to aid in tracking the crack development. Four specimens were fabricated using mortar. One was unreinforced, while the other three were each reinforced with an SMA bar. Of the reinforced specimens, one was used for prestressing, and the other two were used for healing with electricity and induction. Four specimens were fabricated using FRC, and the testing procedure matched that of the mortar specimens. Five specimens were fabricated using UHPC. Four of them followed the same testing procedure as the mortar specimens. The fifth specimen was used to explore prestressing of UHPC with the induction heater.

Figure 2. Flexural specimen design.

The flexural specimens were given three letter identifiers. The first letter indicated their mix design, with “N” for mortar, “F” for FRC, and “U” for UHPC. The second letter indicated the heating method, with “E” for electricity and “I” for induction. The final letter indicated the heating order relative to flexural loading, with “B” for heating before loading and “A” for heating after loading. Four of the flexural specimens were heated before loading to study the effects of SMA on prestressing the concrete. These were denoted as NEB, FEB, UIB, and UEB. Then, all the specimens were loaded in flexure, during which a CMOD gauge was used to track the change in the crack. The load cell reading for each specimen when reaching a CMOD reading of 0.012" is shown in **Figure 3**. When comparing the prestress mortar specimen (NEB) to the average of the specimens with passive SMA (NIA and NEA), 61% more force was needed to reach the same level of damage. Therefore, SMA prestressing was effective at delaying cracks in mortar. For FRC, the SMA prestressing also improved the capacity and therefore delayed the crack development. When comparing FEB to the average capacity of the FRC specimens with passive SMA (FIA and FEA), the prestressing improved the capacity by 18%. When comparing FEB to the unreinforced FRC specimen (FNN), the capacity was improved by 302%. For the UHPC specimens, the UIB specimen demonstrated

the potential advantages of SMA prestressing for UHPC. By comparing UIB to the unreinforced UHPC specimen (UNN), the capacity was seen to have increased by 39%.

Figure 3. Load capacity corresponding to CMOD reading of 0.012”

The results of heating the SMA bar after cracking have occurred are summarized in **Figure 4**. Three of the specimens (NIA, FIA, and UIA) were heated using the induction heater, and three were heated with electrical resistance (NEA, FEA, and UEA). In all specimens, the crack widths reduced once the SMA was heated to its transformation temperature. For the mortar specimens, the cracks reduced by up to 80%. For the FRC specimens, the reduction was as high as 90%. For the UHPC specimens, the reduction was as high as 84%.

Figure 4. Crack closure using (a) electromagnetic induction and (b) electrical resistivity.

3.2 SMA Prestressing in a Precast Concrete Truss

Common concrete girders, such as the AASHTO I-beams and bulb-tees, feature consistent cross-sections along the entire length. While this simplifies the fabrication process, it does not use the material in the most efficient manner. A truss system would use the material more efficiently, as demonstrated by the various steel truss bridges around the world. Bridge trusses have also been built from concrete (Benaim, 2008; Zerin & Kasuga, 2022), but require prestressing in the members subjected to tensile forces. Therefore, this research focused on developing a concrete truss with prestressing using SMA bars. To accomplish this, a precast concrete truss was designed and manufactured. The specimen was 4’ tall and 14’ long. Eight triangular voids were introduced to change the web of the girder into a Howe truss. SMA bars were

embedded in one of the vertical members where high tensile forces are expected. The SMA bars were then heated using the induction machine to produce localized prestressing. Three strain gauges mounted on the surface of the concrete member around the midpoint were used to detect prestressing behavior. The strain gauges were monitored during heating and cooling. After cooling, the strain gauges read an average permanent compressive strain of 301 $\mu\epsilon$, which equates to a prestress of 513 psi in the concrete member. Next, the specimen was loaded in a three-point bending setup. Digital image correlation (DIC) was used to track the development of cracks in the two vertical members. The member without SMA developed cracks first, with cracks appearing near the upper joint once the truss was loaded to 5 kip. Cracks near the joints of the member with SMA began when the truss was loaded to 35 kip, which is 600% higher. This demonstrated that SMA prestressing delayed cracking. Furthermore, the DIC detected cracks only in the center of the member without SMA. These cracks appear as red bands in **Figure 6**.

Figure 6. DIC corresponding to a load of 40 kip

4. CONCLUSIONS

Thirteen small-scale flexural specimens were fabricated and evaluated to assess SMA usage for prestressing and healing mortar, FRC, and UHPC. A large-scale concrete truss was fabricated to assess SMA for prestressing tensile concrete members.

- For the mortar specimens, the specimen with SMA prestressing has 61% higher capacity when compared to the mortar specimens with passive SMA. For the FRC specimens, the specimen with SMA prestressing had 302% higher capacity than the unreinforced FRC specimen. For the UIB specimen, the prestressing provided 39% higher capacity than the unreinforced UHPC specimen.
- The SMA reduced crack widths across all three concrete mix designs. The cracks in the mortar, FRC, and UHPC specimens reduced by 80%, 90%, and 84%, respectively.
- SMA prestressing was effective in the large-scale concrete truss system and produced a prestress of 513 psi. The load corresponding to cracking in the prestressed member was 600% higher than that of the member with only conventional steel.

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Acknowledgement

The authors acknowledge the financial support provided for this study by the Transportation Infrastructure Precast Innovation Center (TRANS-IPIC) through the University Transportation Center program of the US Department of Transportation, Office of the Assistant Secretary for Research and Technology (OST-R) under Grant No. 69A3552348333.